

selectively subcultured every 3 d and maintained in the dark at 25 °C on a gyratory shaker at 120 rpm. The suspension cultures with a high regeneration frequency were established within 1 mo and were suitable for protoplast isolation. The suspension cells were precultured for 3 d on MS liquid medium before they were isolated by enzyme solution.

The isolated protoplasts had dense cytoplasm and many starch grains were seen in them. The highest yield of protoplasts was 2×10^7 g⁻¹ fresh weight cells. Protoplasts were cultured in KPR medium with the membrane nurse culture method. An aliquot of about 0.4 mL liquid KPR medium containing protoplasts (4×10^4) was plated onto a filter (Whatman, 0.2 µm) placed over a layer of nurse cells. Nurse cells were embedded in KPR medium with 1% agarose. After 20-30 d of culture, the cell clusters formed could be seen by the naked eye. The rate of colony formation was about 0.0075%.

When protocalli grew to 1-2 mm in diameter, they were transferred to N6 medium for proliferation and then to MS regeneration medium for plant regeneration. Green plantlets were regenerated from protocalli after 2-3 wk. The average plant regeneration frequency was 3 plants per 1×10^7 protoplasts. The total time from callus initiation to plant regeneration of protoplasts was 4-6 mo.

Our results showed that the presence of nurse cells was required to induce division of protoplasts. In contrast to suspension cultures, it was difficult to isolate pure populations of intact protoplasts directly from the primary calli. Suspension cells with a good growth status, dense cytoplasm, and embryogenic characters played a critical role in successful culture. Protoplast division and colony formation also depended on the age and status of the suspension cells used for preparation of the layer of nurse cells. Establishment of a protoplast regeneration system makes it possible to transfer resistance genes from *O. meyeriana* into cultivated rice. ■

Chinoor: a promising spontaneous mutant and high-quality rice variety of Madhya Pradesh, India

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Chinoor is a low-yielding, late, tall, and lodging-prone indigenous rice variety of Madhya Pradesh, India. It continues to be grown in spite of its low yield because of its high-quality aromatic slender grains that sell for more than twice the price of Mahsuri. Chinoor is also exported to Middle East countries to a limited extent.

We began efforts to reduce duration and plant height of Chinoor in 1995 with a survey in farmers' fields to collect possible spontaneous mutants of interest. Progenies of the 25 single-plant selections made were transplanted along with Chinoor in non-replicated plots for observation. Each progeny plot consisted of 50 plants

grown in 2 rows 20 cm apart. Plants in a row were spaced 15 cm apart. Fertilizer was applied at the rate of 60-40-20 kg NPK ha⁻¹. Twenty plants from each plot were selected randomly and tagged before flowering for observation.

One of the progenies flowered 31 d earlier, matured 38 d earlier, and had 28 cm less height than Chinoor. A comparison of the mutant with Chinoor for grain yield, its components, and some physical quality characters was made (see table).

Although kernel aroma and translucence apparently stayed the same, the mutant recorded 80% higher grain yield plant⁻¹ than Chinoor. This high yield advantage of the mutant resulted largely from its 30% more panicles plant⁻¹ and 20% higher grain weight panicle⁻¹.

The Chinoor mutant, with its higher yield potential and reduced duration and plant height, seems to have potential to not only replace Chinoor but also to be extended to new rice areas where it may enhance productivity and thus profitability of rice cultivation. ■

Comparison of Chinoor mutant with Chinoor, Waraseoni, India, 1996 wet season.

Character	Chinoor mutant (mean ± SD)	Chinoor ^a (mean ± SD)
Days to 50% flowering	89.6 ± 2.4	120.7 ± 2.5
Days to maturity	114.7 ± 1.6	153.0 ± 1.3
Plant height (cm)	113.2 ± 1.9	141.0 ± 2.5
Panicles plant ⁻¹ (no.)	12.8 ± 1.7	8.8 ± 1.5
Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	211.3 ± 4.1	184.1 ± 7.6
1,000-grain weight (g)	15.3 ± 0.2	16.8 ± 0.2
Panicle weight (g)	2.4 ± 0.3	2.0 ± 0.2
Grain length (mm)	8.1 ± 0.1	7.5 ± 0.1
Grain width (mm)	2.1 ± 0.1	1.9 ± 0.1
Kernel length (mm)	6.0 ± 0.1	5.8 ± 0.1
Kernel width (mm)	1.9 ± 0.1	1.7 ± 0.1
L/B (grain)	3.9 ± 0.2	4.0 ± 0.1
L/B (kernel)	3.2 ± 0.2	3.4 ± 0.2
Plant yield (g plant ⁻¹)	31.6 ± 2.0	17.5 ± 2.7

^aAv of 20 individuals.

Multiple submissions. Normally, only one report for a single experiment will be accepted. Two or more items about the same work submitted at the same time will be returned for merging. Submitting at different times multiple notes from the same experiment is highly inappropriate. Detection will result in the rejection of all submissions on that research.